

Commercialization of Filipino Sports: A thing for Sports or Commerce?

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Sports make up the day of almost every Filipino. Ranging from indoor activities, which some of them don't require much physical exertion like chess, to outdoor activities like track and field. The two main reasons for that are the following, first is that they were players themselves in that particular sport. Similar to Frankie Lim, a former Philippine Basketball Association (PBA) player, who is now a coach of NLEX Road Warriors, a team playing in the PBA as well.

With how sports are on the rise, things are becoming more and more exciting. Many young and talented individuals managed to do their academics and sports simultaneously to achieve their goal, especially in the professional league. The commercialization of sports is starting to be a beacon for the sports and this is seen to be the path of many aspiring athletes. All can be pointed to the influences and reaped benefits that can be accounted for, like the promotion of the university (players are coming from), increased athlete value and popularity, and the promotion of the sponsors in a particular sport. A cycle of give and take among players and firms and establishments likely include funds and popularity, which are some key features we can deduce.

Example to prove this deduction is how the latest commercial of Anta Philippines (part of Anta Sports Group) gathered both two PBA's stars, Alvin Patrimonio and Benjie Paras to join with some PBA young stars. The Instagram caption says, "Every legend has a prologue". The promotion of this sportswear brand indicates that they need the support of the basketball stars. With this, their products may be of interest among every individual who is fond of basketball.

In a different light, the commercialization of sports offers promotion to a particular university where a player originally played before coming to the professional league. We know that colleges offer sporting events such as the ever

famous University Athletic Association of the Philippines (UAAP), which is comprised of prestigious institutions all around Metro Manila, National Collegiate Athletic Association (Philippines), State Colleges and Universities Athletic Association (SCUAA) for State Colleges like the Cebu Normal University (CNU), and Private Schools Athletic Association (Philippines) for Private Colleges. Players who were dignified athletes during their collegiate years could be scouted or drafted for the professional league. Example includes Deanna Wong's performance in the Premier Volleyball League (PVL) reflects her training and steady progress back in Ateneo de Manila University Lady Blue Eagles from 2016 to 2020. Indirectly promoting the school as her avenue to grow as a professional player in volleyball.

While sports play a remarkable thing in the lives of Filipinos, there are things that come along the way. Many are for the common good. Even a simple ticket fare to watch the championship match already helps to feed a family of four. There might be some who are unfortunate to get scammed in any way relevant to promoting somebody. While it was never intended in the first place, the fact that key figures' actions may somehow influence other individuals brings to question the idea of them being taken advantage of. This poses a call to reconsider how we view sports. Let's all be reminded that sports are our entertainment and amusement. The thing for commercialization lies on how we intend to take the responsibility of viewing sports. We must bring no harm.